

The Role of Comprehensive Quality Management in Accessing to Lean Manufacturing Criteria in View of Small and Medium Industry Executives

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Abstract

Comprehensive Quality Management is a system that has been emphasized on improving the quality of products and services through the improvement of human resources, processes and equipment and in parallel to reduce the cost of operational field. On the other hand, lean manufacturing, a philosophy and a new attitude to the product, which in this attitude, try to minimize waste and maximize efficiency of facilities, human resources and investment to be achieved. This study investigated the relationship between the components of a comprehensive quality management with lean manufacturing. The study included descriptive - correlation respectively. The statistical population consisted of 285 experts, managers and supervisors of small and medium manufacturing industries of Ardabil province that 134 of them were selected as sample using Morgan table. Research findings were studied using SPSS software and statistical tests Smironov - Kolmogorov and Spearman correlation. The results showed that there is significant relationship between comprehensive quality management variables with lean manufacturing. As well as there is significant relationship was observed between the components of inclusive quality management (top management leadership, support and strategic planning, customer focus, employee training, employee empowerment and teamwork, measurement and quality analysis, quality assurance and outcomes improve quality and productivity) and production lean. Overall effective step is an essential factor that can be an important to achieve lean manufacturing implementation of inclusive quality management in small and medium manufacturing industry

Keywords: comprehensive quality management, Lean manufacturing, Small and medium industries, Managers

Introduction

While the beginning of the third millennium, it seems that as time goes on, less productive methods of managing organizations is similar to an earlier time. Current image in the field of business organizations, a set of processes that aim to create value for its stakeholders and create value for its stakeholders depends on the creation of value in the organization. One of the new production ideas that were raised after mass production, lean production. Toyota's lean production system origin goes back in the 1950s, the time of the Toyota management decided to create a plan for eliminating waste. In general, the view of this production system "waste" is called as each of the factors of production: materials, manpower, machinery spare parts, and time. .. more than the minimum number to be used and does not create any extra value in the product. This approach or thinking, so "pure" that can be called to provide a way through which you can at the lowest (i.e: with less manpower, less equipment, less time and less space) the most work done and at the same time appropriate supply of consumers, they became closer and closer.

Lean Manufacturing is name by "Womack," "Jones" and "Ruvz", after the famous study them in car production systems in the world as «IMVP», the Toyota Production System was established. The results are summarized in the famous book "The machine that changed the world: The Story of Lean Production" to his name and it noted that the concept of simple mechanism to reduce waste production unit to zero. Brown and colleagues also pointed out that Womack et al. (1990) lean manufacturing as a production strategy that in fact the sequence is considered for mass production. This approach focuses on reducing setup time and changes the device for different processes, developed new ideas in the field of humanity resource, as well as advanced techniques in the field of quality; it is seeking to build a broader and more diverse than Japan's automotive market demand. This approach developed to achieve the above objective, intelligent supply chains for materials and parts factories. In addition, the chains created a lean work of distributors and resellers and customers into sections, now.

Total quality management helps as mechanisms to identify indicators of institutional organizational problems on an ongoing basis, monitor the organizational bottleneck, and create sensitivity to timing, employing creative solutions, continuous self-assessment of individual and organizational and process-oriented and integrated approach result-oriented, to prevent crises and help organizations simplify the management decided stems.

Crisis in organizations with a positive vision should be considered as an asset and this is due to the crisis, a series of facilities, structures, human resources, legal empowerment and this idea well combined with each other and a good empathy denominated in organization and organization of unused facilities are used properly.

The proper management is necessary for prevention of crisis of negative. Before the formation of the crisis, is provided with the necessary measures. Comprehensive quality management system is one of the approaches that seriously and operational helps to crisis management and crisis prevention, (Tabatabayi, 2010). Given the importance of the opinions expressed in this study believe that the impact of total quality management is studied lean production of manufacturing industries of Ardabil province.

Lean production

Lean manufacturing system is a comprehensive management system that is applicable to all organizations. Principles and tools of lean, lean management system is part of their managers that apply to improve the quality of products and services, increase market share, increase profitability, focus more on the customer, and respond faster to market changes and more efficient machines.

In dynamic markets and competitive industries and services that require methods that can help overcome the environmental challenges and provide products and services to customers without delay. Such a tool is achieved with lean manufacturing practices.

Current areas of business, presents a new image of the organization that this new approach, the organization is the set of processes that their aim is to create value for customer in your organization.

Organizational plan that wants to follow the above approach first enter the field of sigma and then to level Six Sigma process improvement that is 3.4 errors per million opportunities.

The fundamental concept of lean manufacturing, is eradicating waste and value creation in the organization. Lean manufacturing approach to increase productivity and continuous value creation and minimizing the cost and wasted; in this way it can be the gateway to the land of Sigma to fix the defects, waste and errors evident through quick methods is such as lean manufacturing concepts and techniques, because Sigma is required to increase the rate of exponential increase in reducing defects and waste.

Lean production can be summarized in five principles, with a detailed understanding of these principles and then trying to tie it together, we can complete the implementation of sustainable practices and techniques of Lean solution was in purifying the organization and its processes.

Womack and Jones (1996) in his famous book titled Lean Manufacturing: waste elimination and value creation in organizations have introduced five principles of lean manufacturing. The five principles are:

1. Determining the exact value of any specific product
- 2 - Identifying the product value stream
- 3 - Creating the motion without interrupting the value
- 4 - Allowing customers to pull these values from the manufacturer

5. Pursuing of perfection

The value is basic starting point of lean manufacturing, This is only the final consumer can define value and value has meaning only when it is expressed in terms of a specific product, the product that your customer needs to satisfy a specified price at a certain time. Note that this is manufacturer that creates value.

Total Quality Management

Total Quality Management is the last word when it is used to achieve quality and productivity.

Some researchers continue its scientific management, others find it in a magazine and it's a new paradigm managerial know the system. Total Quality Management is not a plan, but also processes for its implementation in the organization and appropriate conditions necessary.

Checking the readiness of the organization to managers to implement total quality management, visibility will open to be sure, before the implementation of TQM in any organization.

In recent years due to improved quality of service in the public sector, despite the major differences between public sector (government and private sector) has attracted to the managers of this section. Due to the increasing presence of the private sector in the processes of public sector companies, government agencies have to coordinate their own standards of quality and excellence which is heavily used in the private sector (Ankarany, 2008).

Quality of service is known widely used as the main explanation for the success of an organization in today's competitive environment. Any decline in customer satisfaction due to poor quality of service is a concern (Qobadian and Espyler, 2004).

Public institutions must clearly explain its objectives for the end customer are people and citizens, and ensure that the public needs fit the needs of their goals (Alwan and Danaei, 2007).

Many of the efforts of Total Quality Management in the public sector do not lead successfully, because organizations are trying to stereotypical patterns in the private sector (Deywitt and Brady, 2008).

One of the main differences between TQM in the public sector and the private sector is a clear definition of "customer". As well as aspects of quality management are different in the public and private sector (Carlos and Sanchez, 2008).

Today, most organizations have realized which is necessary for their survival continuously reduce its cost, while at the same time that the quality of goods and their services should be to promote outstanding position in the global competitive market. The key to solving this problem is that all manufacturing and service organizations are grappling with the concept of total quality management are summarized. Centers and industrial plants have pioneered using of Total Quality Management.

But in recent years the organization and community centers used as well as an effective strategy from these management practices and successful experiences have achieved in this field (Tabatabai, 2010).

Total Quality Management is a cost-effective system for continuous quality improvement efforts of integration in all levels of the organization, to provide services and products that guarantee customer satisfaction. In fact TQM is seeking to create a culture whereby all employees organize their work improve a view to providing a variety of customer requirements and continuously variable.

In fact, Total Quality Management is the coordinator of systems, human resource management and organizational link why is that a change and Its stable is requiring development two factors human resources

and organizational that are constantly interacting with each other. The goal of Total Quality Management, creation and management system is a system that prevents failure and problems in the performance cycle and Institute. To achieve this research would be reviewed the situation that is causing a problem in their organizations.

So to achieve the objectives of total quality management and key emphasis is necessary prevention affair to regular changes in the attitude of managers and employees to work performance and activities of the organization. This process will cause loss of duality in their behavior. In fact, anyone participates to see and identify the deficiencies in the company's work and activities. In the normal way of quality, two-thirds of the labor force kept away from problems related to the quality. In TQM everyone from the CEO to the lower ranks and even office employees engaged in the process and anyone is responsible for provide services and quality goods production and reduce the "cost of quality" (Sharif Zadeh, 2000).

Literature review

Lean Manufacturing is name by "Womack," "Jones" and "Ruvz", after the famous study them in car production systems in the world as «IMVP», the Toyota Production System was established. The results are summarized in the famous book "The machine that changed the world: The Story of Lean Production" to his name and it noted that the concept of simple mechanism to reduce waste production unit to zero. Brown and colleagues also pointed out that Womack et al. (1990) lean manufacturing as a production strategy that in fact the sequence is considered for mass production, Cheng and Liu (2007) similar studies done on the construction companies in Hong Kong. They write: organization, knowledge and learning are of three essential characteristics of TQM that form a triangle. The three properties are equal importance and independent of each other and these processes are necessary to achieve continuous improvement in the long term (Soleimani and Mohammadi, 2009).

Theories

1. There is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and comprehensive management.
2. There is a significant relationship between lean production and support of senior management and leadership organization.
3. There is a significant relationship between lean production and strategic planning support.
4. There is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and customer orientation.
5. There is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and the identification and training of staff.
6. There is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and employee empowerment and teamwork.
7. There is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and measurement and quality analysis.
8. There is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and quality assurance.
9. There is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and the consequences have been significant improvements in quality and productivity.

Research Methodology

The study carries out descriptive-correlation research in which assessed the relation of the two variables. The study population of this research is including of 285 experts, managers and supervisors of small and medium manufacturing industries of Ardabil province that 134 of them were selected as the sample using Morgan table.

Research Tools

Two questionnaires were used in this study. One questionnaire is related to lean manufacturing that has been translated from a foreign standard questionnaire into Persian. The researchers compared the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. The other questionnaire is included 20 questions of two options. The questionnaire of Total Quality Management (TQM) is done by Moghimi (2009) which contains 8 questions.

Analysis Method

In the first study using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of normality of the data was evaluated and non-normal distribution is obtained because it is used to determine the correlation of Spearman coefficient.

Result

The researchers is attempted to examine the relationship between Total Quality Management and lean production. It is noteworthy that before the expression test to check the hypotheses accepted level of error was considered a percent. Because that the hypothesis accepted significant at a confidence level of 99%, if placed at a lower level will not be accepted.

Table 1: Cronbach's alpha lean manufacturing

Confidence	
Cronbach's alpha	0.819
N item	20

As shown in table 1 Cronbach's alpha values of Lean Manufacturing a questionnaire to 0.819 and it is above 0.7, so reliability is confirmed.

Table 2: Cronbach's alpha of Total Quality Management

Confidence	
Cronbach's alpha	0.803
N item	8

As shown in table 2 Cronbach's alpha values of Lean Manufacturing a questionnaire to 0.803 and it is above 0.7, so reliability is confirmed.

Kolmogorov - Smirnov test is used for normality of variables to distribution of scores of social capital and job satisfaction.

Table 3. Kolmogorov - Smirnov test for normality of variables

comprehensive management of Lean Manufacturing		
correlation coefficient of Spearman comprehensive management	1000	0.718
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134
correlation coefficient of lean manufacturing	1000	0.718
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134

*Sig is considerable: 0.01

Table 4: Correlation coefficient of comprehensive management

	Lean production	Quality Management and Productivity	Quality of Insurance	Analysis of Quality	Team work	Staff training	Customer Orientation	strategic planning	Support and management leadership
N	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134
Mean	3.981	4.3284	3.955	4.448	4.448	3.8955	4.4328	4.4776	4.3881
Standard Deviation	0.341	0.802	.08916	1.0323	0.9247	1.15211	0.0654	0.6571	0.7248
The greatest difference	0.109	0.291	.0236	.0259	0.227	0.249	0.329	0.339	0.305
Positive	0.57	0.201	.0181	0.177	0.161	0.169	0.234	0.214	0.202
Negative	0.109	0.291	0.236	0.259	0.227	0.249	0.329	0.339	0.305
Test	0.109	0.291	0.236	0.259	0.327	0.249	0.329	0.339	0.305

Considering the significantly level is lower than 0.01. Therefore, assuming normal variations is rejected. So the Spearman correlation coefficient used to test the correlation between variables.

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.718 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to zero .therefore a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and comprehensive management.

Table5: Correlation Coefficient of support and leadership of organization senior management

support and leadership of organization senior management		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of support and leadership of organization senior management	1000	0.703
sig (2-tailed)	0	0.013
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.703	1000
sig (2-tailed)	0.013	0
N	134	134

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.703 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to 0.013 .Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and support and leadership of organization senior management.

Table 6: Correlation of strategic planning

strategic planning		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of strategic planning	1000	0.547
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.547	0
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134

*Sig is considerable: 0.01

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.547 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to zero .Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of an organization and support and strategic planning.

Table 7: Correlation of customer orientation

customer orientation		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of customer orientation	1000	0.468
sig (2-tailed)	0	0.008
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.468	1000
sig (2-tailed)	0.008	0
N	134	134

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.468 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to 0.008 .Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and customer orientation.

Table 8: Correlation coefficient of employee identifies and train

employee identifies and train		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of employee identifies and train	1000	0.551
sig (2-tailed)	0	0.004
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.551	1000
sig (2-tailed)	0.004	0
N	134	134

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.551 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to 0.004 .Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and an employee identifies and train.

Table 9: Correlation coefficient of the empowerment and teamwork

The employee empowerment and teamwork		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of The employee empowerment and teamwork	1000	0.898
sig (2-tailed)	0	0.004
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.898	1000
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134

*Sig is considerable: 0.01

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.898 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to zero. Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and the employee empowerment and teamwork.

Table10. Correlation coefficient of measurement of analysis of quality

Measurement of analysis of quality		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of Measurement of analysis of quality	1000	0.484
sig (2-tailed)	0	0.004
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.484	1000
sig (2-tailed)	0.007	0
N	134	134

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.484 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to 0.007. Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and measurement of analysis of quality.

Table11. Correlation coefficient of quality of insurance

quality of insurance		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of quality of insurance	1000	0.904
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.904	1000
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.904 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to zero .Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and quality of insurance.

Table12. Correlation coefficient of quality management and productivity

quality management and productivity		Lean production
Correlation Coefficient of quality management and productivity	1000	0.740
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134
Correlation Coefficient of Lean production	0.740	1000
sig (2-tailed)	0	0
N	134	134

*Sig is considerable: 0.01

Considering that the correlation coefficient value is 0.740 and sig value is less than 0.05 and equal to zero .Therefore, a significant relationship are observed between the variables of lean manufacturing and quality management and productivity.

Discussion and conclusion

TQM is a management philosophy that common needs and goals as an integral knows and are used in trade, industry and services, which guarantee the maximum efficiency and effectiveness of business leaders through the exercise of sovereignty in the process and systems what gives consistency. It Increases efficiency and avoid errors, and the organization also makes sure that all its objectives in order to meet the needs of our customers. On the other hand, lean manufacturing is a philosophy and a new attitude to the product, which in this attitude, try to minimize waste and maximize efficiency of facilities, human resources and investment. Lean manufacturing system is a comprehensive management system that executives use them to improve the quality

of products and services, increase market share, increase profitability, focus more on the customer, respond faster to market changes and employ more efficient machines. The end result of these effects increase profitability and customer loyalty. The findings of this study showed there is a significant relationship between the variables of lean manufacturing and comprehensive management. As well as there is significant relationship was observed between the components of inclusive quality management (top management leadership, support and strategic planning, customer focus, employee training, employee empowerment and teamwork, measurement and quality analysis, quality assurance and outcomes improve quality and productivity) and lean production.

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